

Electrokinetic Remediation of Methyl Blue Contaminated Soil

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ABSTRACT

This work studies the removal of organic pollutants from soil by applying electrokinetic remediation. Model samples with methyl blue contaminated soil were used to evaluate the capacity of the electrokinetic remediation in the treatment and removal of organics from soils. The problem of soil contaminated with dyes from textile industries is a lingering problem which needs to decontaminate using EKR techniques. An EKR tool equipped with a DC electric current (30 voltage, 10amp.) were used in the remediation and the use of Na₂HPO₄ as the electrolyte or processing fluid increased the electro-osmotic flux and desorption of dye from the surface of methyl blue contaminated soil. Different sample concentrations (200ppm, 400ppm and 800ppm) were analyzed with respect to control. The results of dye removal percentage from 200ppm sample were 59%, 63% and 78% for 1, 2 and 3hours respectively. For 400ppm, 51%, 62% and 70% of dye was removed at 1, 2, and 3hours respectively, for 800ppm, 50%, 65% and 73% of dye was removed at 1, 2, and 3hours respectively. From the results of the various sample concentrations, the degradation Increases with time. From the achieved results, the electrokinetic remediation technique could be a promising option for the remediation method for soil and sediments contaminated with organic compounds including dyes.

Keywords: Electrokinetic remediation, disodium hydrogen phosphate, Electro-osmotic, methyl blue, dye removal percentage.

1.0. INTRODUCTION

According to HelpSaveNature soil pollution facts (2005), land contamination and pollution leads to loss of twenty four billion tons of topsoil every year. Soil contamination is one the most ignored concept in the modern world. It is the presence of toxic chemicals (pollutants or contaminants) in soil, in high enough concentrations to pose a risk to human health and the ecosystem. In the case of contaminants which occur naturally in soil, even when their levels are not high enough to pose a risk, soil pollution is still said to occur if the levels of the contaminants in soil exceed the levels that should naturally be present (U.S Environmental protection Agency, Washington D.C, 2004).

All soils, whether polluted or unpolluted, contain a variety of compounds (contaminants) which are naturally present. Such contaminants include metals, inorganic ions and salts (e.g. phosphates, carbonates, sulfates, nitrates), and many organic compounds (such as lipids, proteins, DNA, fatty acids, hydrocarbons, PAHs, alcohols, etc.). These compounds are mainly formed through soil microbial activity and decomposition of organisms (e.g., plants and animals). Additionally, various compounds get into the soil from the atmosphere, for instance with precipitation water, as well as by wind activity or other types of soil disturbances, and from surface water bodies and shallow groundwater flowing through the soil. When the amounts of soil contaminants exceed natural levels (what is naturally present in various soils), pollution is generated. There are two main causes through which soil pollution is generated: anthropogenic (man-made) causes and natural causes in a similar manner, when a piece of land gets polluted due to various factors, it causes harm to the biodiversity and mankind, which is called land pollution.

According to (Ministry of Drinking water and Sanitation, Government of India 2012) Soil contamination or soil pollution as part of land degradation is caused by the presence of xenobiotic (human-made) chemicals or other alteration in the natural soil environment. It is typically caused by industrial activity, agricultural chemicals, or improper disposal of waste. The most common chemicals involved are petroleum hydrocarbons, polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (pesticides, lead, and other heavy metals).

A solution to the problem of soil contamination is soil remediation, Soil remediation is a term used for various processes used to decontaminate soil. It's a method of purifying and revitalizing the soil, it process of removing contaminants in order to protect both the health of population and the environment (Savannah, 2013). There are a number of different processes for soil remediation, each employing a distinct technique for removing contaminants from soil. However, each has an indicated best use, so care must be taken to select the right method of soil remediation services for each unique application. The best approach is determined with a proper soil sampling.

According to (Karim, 2014), electrokinetic processes are relatively new and promising technology being investigated for their potential applications in hazardous waste management specifically in case of high clay containing soils. United State Environmental Protection Agency 2007 (USEPA) has designated electrokinetic method as a viable in-situ process and interested parties are attempting to apply this method at contaminated sites which have inherently low permeability soils and otherwise difficult to decontaminate. Sometimes, spilling and bad management of those effluents provoked the pollution of soils with this kind of organic pollutants (dye), the presence of organics affects the characteristics of soils and provokes the environmental problem, and can even affect public health It is an environmental technique especially developed for the removal of contaminants in soil, sediments and sludge, although it can be applied to any solid porous material.

Electrokinetic remediation is based in the application of a direct electric current of low intensity to the porous matrix to be decontaminated. The effect of the Electric field induces the mobilization and transportation of contaminants through the porous matrix towards the electrodes, where they are collected, pumped out and treated. Main electrodes, anode and cathode, are inserted into the soil matrix, normally inside a chamber which is fill with water or the appropriate solution to enhance the removal of dye (contaminants).

The aim of this study was to assess the potential of remediating methyl blue dye- polluted soil using electrokinetic remediation technique; which was achieved by: determining the effectiveness of electrokinetic remediation for removal of methyl blue dye from soil, determining the effect of various parameters/operating conditions on the remediation process vis-à-vis electrical conductivity, dye concentration, absorbance and pH of the soil, optimizing all variables (e.g. current and voltage levels, processing time, installation and operation costs, etc.

2.0. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Source of Data

The sediment used for electrokinetic remediation was collected from Otamiri River in Federal University of Technology Owerri on 4th June, 2018. 1:00pm.

2.2. Sampling Equipment and Materials

The equipments and materials used during the sampling are:-

- i. Sediment grab
- ii. Sampling bags
- iii. Notebooks and writing materials
- iv. Paper tags
- v. 2mm sieve

2.3. Sample Analysis

2.3.1. Materials and apparatus used in the experiment

- i. Sediment samples.
- ii. DC power supply (LW[®] Longwei 10amp, 30volt).
- iii. 3 Electrokinetic cells (30cm by 10cm).
- iv. Electronic analytical balance (Metra Balance 210g)
- v. Classic digital professional handheld LCD stopwatch. (ABS XL-O13)
- vi. pH meter.(PEC media U.S.A PHS-25)
- vii. UV Spectrophotometer (Lasany[®] Visible Spectrophotometer L1-722)
- viii. Digital pH, Conductivity and Temperature Meter (Labtech[®])
- ix. 1* 100*100mm 304 2B Surface stainless sheet plate
- x. 1pc 100mm ×100mm TC4/ GR5 B54 Metal thin titanium plate 0.5mm thickness sheet foil.
- xi. Beakers, measuring cylinders and volumetric cylinder and spatula
- xii. Vials
- xiii. Universal Alligator probe(banana plug cable)
- xiv. Sterile pipette
- xv. Conical flask
- xvi. Magnetic stirrer
- xvii. Plastic containers
- xviii. Filter paper
- xix. Disposable hand gloves

- xx. Sartorius weighing balance.
- xxi. Inverter

2.3.2. Reagents Used

- i. Sodium hydroxide.
- ii. Sulphuric acid.
- iii. Monosodium di-hydrogen phosphate.
- iv. Potassium chloride.
- v. Distilled water,
- vi. Methyl blue dye

2.4. Laboratory Analysis

2.4.1. Determining the Different Concentrations Used and dye stock solutions

775g of dried sediments was contaminated with different concentrations of dye solutions depending on the standards.

Different standards of concentration was prepared (200ppm, 400ppm, 800ppm)

i. For 200ppm

Using the dilution formular

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$$

Looking for V_1

$$V_1 = \frac{C_2V_2}{C_1}$$

Where

$$C_2=200$$

$$V_2=250$$

$$C_1=1000$$

$$V_1 = \frac{200 \times 250}{1000} = 50\text{ml}$$

ii. For 400ppm

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$$

Looking for V_1

$$V_1 = \frac{C_2V_2}{C_1}$$

Where

$$C_2=400$$

$$V_2=250$$

$$C_1=1000$$

$$V_1 = \frac{400 \times 250}{1000} = 100\text{ml}$$

iii. For 800PPM

$$C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$$

Looking for V_1

$$V_1 = \frac{C_2V_2}{C_1}$$

Where

$$C_2=800$$

$$V_2=250$$

$$C_1=1000$$

$$V_1 = \frac{800 \times 250}{1000} = 200\text{ml}$$

Table 1: Different Concentrations and Volumes

Concentrations in ppm	Volume
200	50ml
400	100ml
800	200ml

2.4.2. Electrokinetic Remediation Cell Setup

The EKR system used in this study was set up as shown in Figure 1 below, it consists of soil compartments, two electrode chambers, a power supply and a data recorder, etc.

Graphite electrodes with the length 8-10cm and a diameter of 4-6mm were used for both anode and cathode. The sample, 775g of dyes polluted sediment was loaded into the soil chambers.

Figure 1: Electrokinetic cell setup

The processing fluid or electrolyte was inserted to the electrode chamber solution to enhance the electrical conductivity of the system, improving desorption of dye from sediments particles and to increase the transportation rate of the pollutants from the sediment. The pH of both sides were controlled by 0.1M of Hydrochloric acid. A D.C power supply of 30v and 10amps was applied between the anode and cathode and monitoring date was taken periodically by using a midi logger (GL2000, Graphtee).

Figure 2: A D.C power supply

2.4.3. Electrokinetic Remediation Process

After the completion of the EKR treatment, the soil was taken from the soil chambers carefully, divided into three sections (S1, S2, S3) from anode to cathode direction, the sample soil was left all day for drying procedure. The samples then analyzed for pH, electrical conductivity and dye concentrations for each sections.

pH Determination

- 20g of contaminated sediment was weighed using electrical analytical balance and transferred into 100ml beaker
- 40ml of distilled water was added and stirred with a glass rod
- Allow to stand for 30mins with intermittent stirring
- To the soil suspension in the beaker, immerse the electrode and determine the pH using pH meter.

Electrical conductivity determination

- 10g of contaminated sediment was weighed using electrical analytical balance and was transferred into a measuring bottle
- 50ml of distilled water was added and was shaken at 15rpm for 1hour to dissolve soluble salts
- The conductometer was calibrated according to manufacturers instruction using potassium chloride.

Dye concentration determination

- 4g of contaminated sediment was weighed using electrical analytical balance and 32ml of electrolyte (0.1m of Na_2HPO_4) at pH 8-12
- Shake for 3hours using the shaker at 150rpm
- Centrifuge at 4000rpm for 10-15mins
- Finally, the dye concentrations were determined by absorbance measurements using UV visible spectrophotometer at the wavelength of disperse blue (670) as maximum wavelength of methyl blue.

3.0. RESULT PRESENTATION

The results of the electrokinetic remediation that is conducted in electrokinetic cell divided into three compartments (S1,S1,S3) are shown in this chapter, the performances of the electrolyte(Monosodium dihydrogen phosphate) and current applied across the compartments S1,S2,S3 are shown with respect their absorbance, electrical conductivity and pH.

Table 2: Different Standards and their Absorbance

S/N	Concentrations	Absorbance
1.	200	2.639
2.	400	2.649
3.	600	2.658
4.	800	2.670
5.	1000	2.684

Figure 3: Calibration Curve of Methyl Blue

3.1. Electrical Conductivity and pH

Results for 200PPM (1 hour)

Table 3: Results of Conductivity and pH (200ppm)

S1		S2		S3	
pH	EC	pH	EC	pH	EC
5.84	0.61	5.83	0.59	5.83	0.56
Control Before Passing The Current					
pH		EC			
5.80		0.466			

Results for 400PPM (2 hours)

Table 4: Results of conductivity and pH 400ppm

S1		S2		S3	
pH	EC	pH	EC	pH	EC
5.58	0.201	5.55	0.19	5.50	0.12
Control before passing the Current					
pH		EC			
5.6		0.201			

Results for 800PPM (3 hours)

Table 5: Results of Conductivity and pH of 800ppm

S1		S2		S3	
pH	EC	pH	EC	pH	EC
6.06	0.271	6.00	0.262	5.58	0.20
Control before passing the current					
pH		EC			
5.82		0.165			

3. 2. Absorbance Results

Table 6: Absorbance Results for 200PPM

Absorbance results for 200PPM			
Time (hours)	Anode (S1)	Middle (S2)	Cathode (S3)
0	0.41	0.41	0.41
1	0.121	0.20	0.190
2	0.102	0.180	0.160
3	0.071	0.10	0.130

Figure 4: Graph showing the effect of degradation for 200ppm

Table 7: Absorbance results for 400ppm

Absorbance results for 400PPM			
Time (hours)	Anode (S1)	Middle (S2)	Cathode (S3)
0	0.51	0.51	0.51
1	0.171	0.310	0.280
2	0.152	0.240	0.190
3	0.120	0.180	0.160

Figure 5: Graph showing the effect of degradation for 400ppm

Table 8: Absorbance results for 800ppm

Absorbance results for 800PPM			
Time (hours)	Anode (S1)	Middle (S2)	Cathode (S3)
0	0.6	0.6	0.6
1	0.18	0.41	0.31
2	0.15	0.30	0.21
3	0.12	0.21	0.14

Figure 6: Graph showing the effect of degradation for 800ppm

Observations

- i. It was observed that, when the DC Power supply was set at 30v and 10amps and current and voltage was applied across the cell containing methyl blue dye contaminated sediments, the current drops as the time increases
- ii. At anode the fluid coming out was yellowish in colour with white precipitate while the cathode contained a brownish fluid and precipitate.
- iii. At cathode there was a foam or bubble formation at the base of electrode and none was observed at the anode.
- iv. During the electrokinetic remediation a splint sound was observed at both the electrodes, confirming the degradation process and effectiveness of EKR technique.

Table 9: Table showing the current and voltage changes with time

Time	16mins	30mins	42mins	52mins	1hour
Voltage	30.1V	30.0V	29.8V	29V	29V
Current	0.25 amp	0.24 amp	0.23 amp	0.22 amp	0.20 amp

4.0. DISCUSSION

The results obtained could have been influenced by various factors including moisture content, pH, voltage gradient, grain size, total ionic concentration, presence of other ions and type of soil/sediment.

The results showed that the longer the time, the more effective the degradation of methyl contaminated sediment, also degradation is more pronounced at the anode and cathode sites and lesser at middle (S2).

The objective of this experiment was to determine the efficiency of eletrokinetic technology on removing methyl blue dye from a sediment artificially contaminated at the lab was tested.

Methyl blue is commonly used in industries, its complex structure with several aromatic rings and bonds makes it appropriate as a model organic pollutant. It has a bright blue. Flash blue brown powder. It is easy to dissolve in the cold water and hot water (for blue solution), soluble in ethanol is green light blue. Meet strong sulfuric acid is red brown, it will be a violet after diluted. It is mainly used to produce pure blue and black ink.

The desorption of MB from sediment can be achieved by the addition of the electrolyte, in order to improve this electrokinetics process ,it is necessary to add an electrolyte that increases the electric conductivity and favors desorption of dye from a contaminated sediment sample. Mono-sodium di phosphate was found to have been very effective in the extraction of dye from mineral matrix; in fact it was used in the extraction of methyl blue from contaminated sediment in the analytical procedure, it is a strong electrolyte which is completely dissociated in solutions. When a solution of the electrolyte is used it dissociates into cations and anions which are transported through methyl blue contaminated sediment from one point to the other by the effect of electric field, the presence of mono sodium di-phosphate increases the conductivity and favors the desorption of methyl blue from the sediment particles.

Thus desorbed methyl blue can be transported through electro-osmosis and/or electro-migration towards the electrode chambers. For this reason the mono sodium di phosphate was selected as our processing fluid, filling the anode to cathode with 0.1M mono sodium di phosphate.

4.1. Effect of Adding Electrolyte as a Fluid Processing.

The electrolyte helps in increasing the conductivity and effective desorption of dye, it has a great influence on the electrokinetic remediation of sediment contaminated with methyl blue dyes, the electrolyte used in this study is Monosodium di-hydrogen phosphate. When distilled water was used as a migrating media, around 43% of dyes still remaining in soil sections, the direction of MB removal was found from anode to cathode, the percentage of MB removal increased when the electrolyte was added, where a total of 25.6% of MB remained in the soil

sections (S1, S2, S3). Here 37.8% of MB was found in the cathode chamber and total percentage of MB removed from the soil sections is 84.5%.

4.2. Effects of dye ageing on the removal percentage of the dye

I also studied about the other considerations related with the ageing effect on the removal process of pollutants in the EKR system. All of dyes in this study were polluted in one day or 24hours. There are many types of ageing such as physical, biological and chemical ageing (Randall 1986.) as well as phytochemical degradation, thermal degradation, chemical attack and mechanical stress (Hale *et al.*, 2011), it will be interesting point to conduct the experiment by considering the effect of ageing of dye in the soil. It has been hypothesized that ageing involves diffusion into the soil microspores, portioning into the soil organic matter, strong surface adsorption, or a combination of these processes. Since ageing effect of the dye in the soil is important, a study should be conducted to determine whether time that a compound remains in the soil affects the removal ability of the dye in the EKR system.

Observations made from the experiments, it is observed that the higher the time the dyes remain in the soil the lower the rate of degradation or removal.

The results decreased when compared with the removal of MB of only 1 day of contamination. And the 30 days ageing treatment when compared with 1 day decreased by 25%.

200ppm

The amount of methyl blue dye removed from the sediment was 59%, 63% and 78% for 1,2and 3hours respectively.

From Figure 4 which is a graph showing the effect of degradation for 200ppm, it indicates that the more the time of remediation the more effective the removal percentage and from the plot the degradation is more effective at S1 (Anode) and S3 (cathode) than the middle S2 because both S1 and S3 are closed to the both electrodes.

400ppm

The amount of methyl blue dye removed from the sediment was 51%, 62% and 70% for 1,2and 3hours respectively.

From Figure 5 which is a graph showing the effect of degradation for 400ppm, it indicates that the more the time of remediation the more effective the removal percentage and from the plot the degradation is more effective at S1 (Anode) and S3 (cathode) than the middle S2 because both S1 and S3 are closed to the both electrodes.

800ppm

The amount of methyl blue dye removed from the sediment was 50%, 63% and 73% for 1,2and 3hours respectively.

From Figure 6 which is a graph showing the effect of degradation for 800ppm, it indicates that the more the time of remediation the more effective the removal percentage and from the plot the degradation is more effective at S1 (Anode) and S3 (cathode) than the middle S2 because both S1 and S3 are closed to the both electrodes.

5.0. CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results of this research clearly showed that the addition of electrolyte and controlling pH value during the treatment could reveal the optimum condition for the electrokinetic remediation process.

Furthermore, the dyes removal was really increased from the soil sections. Moreover, the process was improved by addition of adequate electrolytes since their presence in the anode and cathode chambers favored the electrical conductivity and desorption of pollutants or contaminants from the soil or from the surface of the soil. Moving directions of the dye, pH value changes, the electrical conductivity, concentration after the EKR process, for three sections (S1, S2, and S3) from anode site to cathode site, were different for any kind of dye contaminant. The characteristic and behavior of the removal system was different among all tested dye contaminants, since there were differences of the dye structures and charges of the dyes. Thus it can be concluded that the operating conditions, especially the pH value into the soil chamber soil sample, are decisive parameters to achieve the best remediation process. It can be concluded that the ageing of the dye affects the removal percentage of dye. The longer the time of ageing treatment, the smaller the removal percentage of dye. Considering the achieved results in this study, the electrokinetic remediation technique could be a promising option for the remediation method for soil and sediments contaminated with organic compounds including dyes

6.0. REFERENCES

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